

DEVELOPMENT OF AN ECO-FRIENDLY TONER/PRINT REMOVER USING AQUEOUS ACETONEPrateek V Shettar¹Sanjay S S^{2*}Shashiprabha³

¹Student, Department of Electrical & Electronics Engineering, Sri Dharmasthala Manjunatheshwara Institute of Technology (SDMIT), Ujire-574 240, (Karnataka) India.

²Assistant Professor, Department of Chemistry, Sri Dharmasthala Manjunatheshwara Institute of Technology (SDMIT), Ujire-574 240, (Karnataka), India.

³Assistant Professor, PG Department of Chemistry, Sri Dharmasthala Manjunatheshwara College (Autonomous), Ujire-574 240, (Karnataka) India.

*E-mail : sanjayss@sdmit.in

ABSTRACT

Toner remover solution is used to erase the toner/print on the waste/used printed papers. A waste paper sheet full of texts or images is subjected to the action of toner remover solution, toner/print will be removed completely and the paper is ready for reuse. Present invention enables to reuse waste/used printed papers with slight change in the paper surface quality. It is an eco-friendly, non-hazardous process and a viable method to erase the toner/print. Recycle & reuse is the current global demand, present process facilitates the reuse of printed papers by eliminating the tedious paper recycling.

Keywords:

Toner remover, aqueous acetone, printed papers, reuse of paper, paper surface.

INTRODUCTION

In the present digital world, there is an extensive use of email and numerous apps embedded in smart phones for quick communication and sharing the information. In spite of this, the printing media has kept its own importance. Printing media plays a vital role in delivering the news, knowledge, information etc to the mankind. Printing industry uses variety of toners to print the information on the paper. Handling the waste or used printed papers is an uphill task. It can be reused, if the toner is effectively removed from the paper surface. Prior art findings gave numerous methodologies which are successfully implemented to reuse the waste printed paper by effectively removing the toner/print.

A study [1] had reported the multistep process to remove the toner/print from the waste printed paper surface. The process involves the use of erasable toner followed by heat treatment method and finally cold air blow pathway to remove the toner from the paper surface. A study [2] had reported the removal of toner/print from a photocopy paper by preheating the paper sheet in a controlled low temperature oven. Heat treatment makes the toner to loosen up, it is made to come in contact with an adhesive surface and later separated. Press contact with the adhesive surface removes the loosened up toner/print effectively and makes the paper ready for the reuse. A study [3] had reported

the use of an apparatus and few processes for creating a writable and an erasable printing using an effective nanoparticle toner. A study [4] had reported the use of solvents to remove the toner/print without damaging the underlying source paper. The solvent composition is a mixture of 60% dimethylsulphoxide (DMSO) and 40% chloroform (CHCl₃). The waste printed paper is soaked for 4-5minutes in the solvent composition, immersion removes 10% of the toner content only. Gentle rubbing (removes 50%) and use of ultrasonic agitation (removes 80%) enhances the toner elimination from the paper surface. A study [5] had reported the use of an abrasive process to remove the toner from the waste printed paper. The impact of varying abrasive grit size, speed, distance, load and repetition over the toner removal concept is tabulated. By applying 22m grit silicon oxide abrasive with a force of 0.3N and rubbing at a speed of 6m/s for approximately 6s on each character, makes the waste printed sheet to loose its toner and is ready for reuse. A study [6] had reported the use of kerosene with mild agitation to remove the toner from the waste printed paper surface. However by using sodium hydroxide (NaOH) alone, only 3.8% of toner was liberated from the paper surface. Using undiluted kerosene had raised the toner removal impact to 98.1%. Kerosene emulsion was also tried with a removal impact to an extent of 80.1%. It is recommended to carry out NaOH treatment in advance to kerosene treatment process, which is critical to enhance the toner liberation/ removal from the surface of paper. A study [7] had reported the use of various organic solvents to remove toner, either as alone or as solvent combinations. The effect of solvents on mechanical, physical and optical properties of paper was estimated.

In the present invention, we report the reuse of waste/used printed papers by effectively removing the toner/print using a novel toner/print removal solution. An aqueous solvent was prepared by using acetone and demineralized water (DM water) to generate the toner/print remover solution. Present work also narrates the pathway of toner/print removal from the paper surface using aqueous acetone. Entire invention revolves around the reuse of printed papers by eliminating paper recycling process, which would consume cost as well as time. Present invention is an eco-friendly process, since non-hazardous solvent is used to develop a toner/print remover solution.

EXPERIMENTAL

Materials and Methods

Printed papers (A-4, 80GSM) were collected for the experimental purpose. Commercial grade acetone was used for the solution preparation using DM water. A soft rubber tipped scrapper was used to facilitate the toner/prints removal over the paper in wet condition after subjecting the printed paper with aqueous acetone solution. Plastic dropper (2.5mL capacity) was used to add the aqueous acetone solution over the printed paper. A soft bristle tooth brush was used to clean the wet paper surface gently. Hot air oven was used to dry the wet paper after the toner/print removal at 40-45 deg C for 15minutes. Paper surface was gently wiped using a soft cloth (nano-fiber). Iron box was used for the mild heat press to improve the paper surface after the toner elimination.

General procedure

In the present work, aqueous acetone was used as the toner/print removal agent from the waste printed paper. It was prepared by mixing acetone (80%) and DM water (20%). Using the dropper aqueous acetone solution was added over the printed paper to make it wet. Toner/print removal was facilitated by a soft rubber tipped scrapper initially and by soft bristle tooth brush later, gentle rubbing and mild brushing over the toner/print removes it completely. Wet paper was dried at 40-45 deg C in hot air oven for 15minutes. A mild heat press can be induced to make the surface of paper smooth and lustrous. Before taking the paper for reprint, surface was gently wiped using a soft cloth (nano-fiber) to eliminate the eruptive paper dust. Experiment was repeated for the reprinted paper using fresh aqueous acetone solution. Experiment was performed in two cycles, Cycle-1 (using waste printed paper) and Cycle-2 (reprint over processed cycle-1 paper) as illustrated in **Table.1**.

Table.1: Outline of the experiment performed to erase/remove the print/toner

Sl. No	Experiment	Paper quality	Inference
1	Cycle-1	Waste/used printed A-4 paper/sheet	Mild roughness observed over the paper after drying and processing
2	Cycle-2	After the reprint over the processed cycle-1 paper/sheet	Noticeable roughness was observed over the paper after drying and processing

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Selection of toner removal solution

Various solvents and their aqueous solutions were used to erase the toner/print. Details of the experiment were tabulated in **Table.2**, with elusive conclusions for the selection of toner/print removal solution. Single solvents such as acetone $\{(CH_3)_2CO\}$, dimethylformamide (DMF), dimethylsulfoxide (DMSO), methanol (CH_3OH) etc were tried but did not get the satisfactory results. Various aqueous solvents were applied over the printed surface and the results led to further experimental ventures. Higher water content in the solution induced paper roughening/rupturing, whereas with solutions having lower water content proved effective in completely removing toner/print safely. Presence of substantial quantity of water along with solvent was found to be essential for the effective toner/print elimination. The aqueous solution of acetone (80:20) had shown considerable impact in removing toner/print and it also keeps the paper surface better for the reprint purpose. Selection of the toner removal solution was finalized by validative/repetitive experiments using aqueous acetone solution (80:20).

Table.2: Tabulation of experimental trials performed using various solvents and their aqueous solutions for toner/print removal from the printed papers

Sl. No	Erase agent used	Inference/Conclusion
1	Acetone $\{(CH_3)_2CO\}$	Toner/print was slowly erased over the printed paper
2	Dimethylformamide (DMF)	Toner/print was not removed
3	Methanol (CH_3OH)	Toner/print was not removed
4	Dimethylsulfoxide (DMSO)	Toner/print was removed but genuine delay in paper drying
5	Aqueous acetone (50:50)	Paper surface got ruptured at various places
6	Aqueous acetone (70:30)	Intense roughness observed over the processed paper
7	Aqueous acetone (80:20)	Mild roughness was observed over the processed paper
8	Aqueous acetone (90:10)	Toner/print elimination was incomplete

Process fine tuning

Various applicative methods were tried to remove the toner/print by using aqueous acetone solution (80:20) as described in **Table.3**. Mere application or dipping the printed paper in the toner remover solution will not remove the toner/print, it only loosens the toner. Toner/print area after being made wet with the toner removal solution has be gently disturbed by rubber tipped scrapper initially and later gentle cleaning by soft bristle tooth brush to eliminate the toner/print contents from the paper surface. The wet the paper has to be dried for 15minutes in hot air oven at 40-45 deg C and later surface was gently wiped using soft cloth (nano-fiber), removes the surface bound tiny toner dust. Finally the paper was given a mild thermal press to induce the essential smooth and lustrous surface features using the iron box. **Fig.1** shows the initial input paper having the toner/print, **Fig.2** shows the paper surface after the process completion.

Fig.1: Input paper sample

Fig.2: Paper sample after the toner/print removal

Table.3: Tabulation of methods followed for effective toner/print removal from the paper surface using toner removal solution

Sl. No	Method	Inference/Conclusion
1	Adding the aqueous acetone solution by dropper on to the print areas	Loosens the toner, will not removes it from the surface completely
2	Adding the aqueous acetone solution by dropper on to the print areas and rubbing gently using rubber tipped scrapper followed by brush touch	Effectively removes the toner/print from the paper surface
3	Dipping the paper in aqueous acetone solution	Loosens the toner, will not removes it from the surface completely
4	Dipping the paper in aqueous acetone solution and rubbing gently using rubber tipped scrapper followed by brush touch	Effectively removes the toner/print from the paper surface

Recovery and reuse aspects

Aqueous acetone solution was tried to recover after the toner/print removal from the paper surface. The solution had suspensions of toner particles, hence it was filtered using the Whatman filter paper under mild vacuum. The same recovered aqueous acetone solution was reused as the toner remover solution in a separate experiment, induced rupturing of paper at various places. It is due to the loss/escape of acetone (highly volatile) during the sequential steps (removal and filtration process), lead to severe enhancement of water content in the solution. As the water content increases in the aqueous acetone mixture, possibility of paper surface deterioration/rupturing is more. A freshly prepared aqueous acetone solution (80:20) for each new trial was found to be effective in eliminating the print/toner without damaging the paper surface. If the toner removal solution was prepared in bulk then it has to be stored in air tight containers to prevent the gradual acetone evaporation.

Cycle 1, experiment was performed primarily focusing on the removal of toner/print from the waste printed paper. Mild roughness was observed over the paper after drying and processing. Same processed paper was reused for the experiment in Cycle 2, experiment was performed with noticeable roughness appearance over the paper surface after drying and processing. Mild surface deterioration was observed after the reuse experimentation, still the paper could be used for the printing purposes.

CONCLUSION

In the present invention, an efficient solution to remove toner/prints over the printed paper has been developed successfully. Aqueous acetone solution (80:20) removes the print/toner and facilitates to reuse the paper for re-printing. A novel, non-hazardous, eco-friendly and cost effective methodology was invented to reuse the paper by completely removing the print/toner without significant damage on to the paper surface. Experimental outcomes support the successful utility of the paper for re-printing after 1st time removal of print/toner. Subsequent reuse of papers after print/toner removal process slowly degenerates the paper quality by making it a rough surface progressively. Duration of the experimental exposure led to the gradual evaporation of acetone from the toner removal solution, hence keeps away the concept of recovery and reuse of the solution. A compact, captive and an automated system will help to remove the print/toner from the paper in bulk along with systemic utilization of the used toner removal solution.

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